

Deliverable D3.1

Mapping the policy & regulation landscape in Ireland on Climate Change

Document Information

Project name & acronym	CLIMATUDE: Understanding Irish people's attitudes, beliefs and values related to climate change
Funding Agency	Environmental Protection Agency
Grant agreement #	2024-CE-1284
Project duration	02-Jan-25 to 01-Jul-28
Deliverable	D3.1: Mapping the policy & regulation landscape in Ireland on Climate Change
Related work package	WP3
Document date	05 September 2025
Dissemination level	PU
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Editor	Niall P. Dunphy

Suggested citation:

Gough, R., Lennon, B., & Dunphy N.P. (2025). *Mapping the policy & regulation landscape in Ireland on Climate Change*. CLIMATUDE EPA-funded project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18854051/10.5281>

About CLIMATUDE

CLIMATUDE deploys a programme of engaged research to develop an in-depth understanding of Irish people's attitudes, beliefs and values related to climate change. In realising this, the project considers perceptions and attitudes to specific climate mitigation and adaptation measures, attitudes to wider governance structures and to decision-making processes.

The project is mapping the knowledge and perceptions of Irish people relating to climate change and its societal implications and developing an in-depth understanding of how people's attitudes to climate change are shaped by their sources of information, social networks, and wider public discourse. It will explore how their beliefs and values are influenced by their socio-demographic attributes, especially gender, life-stage, socio-economic privilege, and educational attainment.

The outcomes of the CLIMATUDE feed into future research within the EPA's climate change pillar and inform ongoing activities within the National Dialogue on Climate Action and Local Authority Climate Action plans. Project outcomes contribute towards the inclusion of climate justice principles in the design and implementation of climate actions and assist in building public support, fostering an accelerated movement towards a just transition.

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Table of Contents

1. INTRODUCTION.....	7
1.1. CONTEXT	7
1.2. BACKGROUND.....	8
1.3. STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT.....	9
2. METHODOLOGY	10
2.1. INTRODUCTION	10
2.2. THE LITERATURE REVIEW	10
3. POLICY AND REGULATORY CONTEXT	11
3.1. INTRODUCTION	11
3.2. OVERVIEW OF INFLUENCE ON ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY IN IRELAND	12
3.3. INTERNATIONAL CLIMATE CHANGE POLICY	22
3.4. EUROPEAN CLIMATE CHANGE POLICY	25
3.5. IRELAND'S RELATIONSHIP TO INTERNATIONAL CLIMATE CHANGE POLICY.....	27
4. IRISH CLIMATE POLICY DOMAIN	31
4.1. INTRODUCTION	31
4.2. ORGANISATIONAL ENGAGEMENT IN NATIONAL LEGISLATIVE PROCESSES	31
4.3. CITIZEN PARTICIPATION.....	35
5. IRISH CLIMATE POLICIES AND REGULATIONS	37
5.1. INTRODUCTION	37
5.2. OVERVIEW OF INFLUENCE ON ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY IN IRELAND	38
5.3. POLICY ENGAGEMENT IN IRELAND.....	40
6. CONCLUSIONS.....	47
7. BIBLIOGRAPHY	50

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an overview of the current landscape of environmental policy in Ireland. Ireland's climate governance framework is centred on the Climate Action Plan and the Climate Action and Low Carbon Development (Amendment) Act 2021, which introduced legally binding carbon budgets aligned with EU climate targets. This deliverable examines the governance and implementation of these policies with a view to understanding how policy both shapes, and is shaped by, Irish public attitudes, beliefs and values regarding climate change. The report begins by outlining the key cultural, social, political and economic factors influencing Irish environmental policy. These factors are, of course, complex and continually evolving. While it is beyond the scope of the report to focus exclusively on this dimension, a concise overview of the dominant influences is provided as a foundation for the policy and landscape analysis that follows.

Political factors influencing Irish environmental policy are then assessed. Ireland's democratic status and EU membership are noted to be of particular significance in this context. Governmental will — that is, the ability of elected officials to effectively oversee climate policy — also plays a role. The rise of global instability (and energy insecurity), in particular the Russian invasion of Ukraine, and the lobbying of fossil fuel companies and other vested interests are identified as factors with the potential to shape policy. The influence of economic factors (and interests) on Irish environmental policy is also considered and structural challenges to policy implementation in particular the high emissions produced by Ireland's agricultural sector and the unique difficulties of decarbonisation in the context of an island energy system.

The dominant thematic forces in Irish climate policy were identified. An emphasis was found to be placed on technical solutions to climate change with only limited attention given to socio-cultural responses. The main "influence clusters" associated with Irish environmental policy are described and the influence of several institutionally important and economically powerful organisations, most notably within the agricultural sector are also noted. The global and European climate policy context is assessed; we note that Ireland's relationship with European climate policy is not straightforward. This can be attributed to several factors, including Ireland's somewhat transactional relationship with the EU, its neoliberal orientation, its island status, and the ensuing relative difficulty of decarbonisation compared to others.

The report concludes with a broad analysis of Irish people's engagement with environmental policy. The influence of socio-demographic specificities (*e.g.*, age, gender) and personality traits (*e.g.*, preference for hierarchy-based social structures) can shape individual attitudes towards climate change is considered. Also relevant in this regard is the 'localism' encouraged (perhaps it might even be said necessitated) by the Irish PR-STV voting system. The report highlights systems of participatory

governance such as the Citizen's Assembly, commenting on the relationship between these initiatives and public participation more generally on effective climate policy implementation. The potential of media coverage (perhaps coupled with and influenced by lobbying campaigns) to impact climate policy is also underlined. The report also notes that media representations of climate change frequently limit public imagination about sustainable futures by virtue of their recourse to visual shorthands for climate disaster which can provoke climate fatigue and ambivalence.

In summary, the report provides a broad overview of the contemporary landscape of influences on Irish public attitudes towards climate change. This report has indicated areas of particular interest as well as highlighting areas where further research is required to deepen our understanding of the underlying factors which dictate Irish people's beliefs about and attitudes towards climate change. This report is intended to serve as a foundation for the realisation of the remainder of CLIMATUDE project research.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

CLIMATUDE is an EPA-funded research project that seeks to develop an in-depth understanding of Irish people's attitudes, beliefs and values related to climate change. In realising this, the project considers perceptions and attitudes to specific climate mitigation and adaptation measures, attitudes to the wider governance structures and decision-making processes. This research approach builds on a participatory research methodology successfully deployed in (and iteratively refined through, projects such as ENTRUST (Horizon2020, 2015-18), Imagining2050 (EPA/SEAI, 2018-21), ENCLUDE (Horizon2020, 2021-24), and ACCEPT (Horizon 2020, 2021-24), *etc.* This mixed-methods approach involves deploying proven research methods, involving a systematic review of literature, survey of citizens, semi-structured interviews, workshops, and an asynchronous dialogue (using a modified Delphi-panel approach). CLIMATUDE has adopted a co-creation approach with citizens being engaged to co-produce knowledge with the researchers. This work is informed by the recent Creative C-Change project (Creative Ireland, 2021-2023) and is benefiting from cross-fertilisation with outputs from the JustCities Hub project (EPA 2024-28), which is running concurrently.

CLIMATUDE aims to provide a mapping of the knowledge and perceptions of Irish people relating to climate change and its societal implications. It is developing an in-depth understanding of how people's attitudes to climate change are shaped by their sources of information, social networks and wider public discourse. It is exploring how their beliefs and values are influenced by their socio-demographic attributes, especially gender, life-stage, socio-economic privilege, and educational attainment. In this work the researchers are leveraging their involvement in the SHIFT COST action¹ to discuss emerging outcomes and compare with international experience.

In particular, the role of gender will be illuminated by intersectional analyses of risk-related behaviour and attitudes towards climate change and will assess how multiple identities and social positions, combine to shape attitudes. These analyses will be integrated within a transitions management framework which takes account of the complex meshing of human values and identities with the socio-technical systems that shape them. Here the project team will leverage their work in the International Energy Agency UsersTCP task 'EmPOWERing All: Just and Inclusive Energy Transitions'² in which the PI and one of the co-PIs are the Irish participants.

¹ SHiFT (CA21166) Social Sciences and Humanities for Transformation and Climate Resilience (European Cooperation in Science and Technology COST, 2021-2026]. <https://shift-cost.eu>

² <https://userstcp.org/empowering-all-task/>

There is general acceptance (albeit not universal) in Ireland that climate change is a real phenomenon and moreover a significant threat to our planet (O'Mahony *et al.*, 2024), with most people accepting that the causes are anthropogenic. However, notwithstanding the high regard of science in Irish society³, there remains an antipathy amongst a certain cohort towards climate science. This antipathy means that such people are more susceptible to the online misinformation, disinformation and malinformation (MDM) that is increasingly common, not least on the topic of climate change. The role of *personal interest bias*⁴ in climate discourse only often serves to exacerbate the spread of such misinformation whether knowingly or unknowingly. The importance of trust in communications on climate change will be examined, considering both traditional and newer forms of media. The role that MDM can play in undercutting social trust and its impact on climate discourse and wider political debates will be considered. Trust between citizens and their governments is crucial for the legitimacy and functioning of democracies (Brezzi *et al.*, 2021). Accordingly, specific recommendations on countering disinformation related to climate change during the work of this project.

It is planned that the outcomes of the CLIMATUDE will be fed into future research within the EPA's climate change pillar and into ongoing activities within the National Dialogue on Climate Action and Local Authority Climate Action plans within Ireland. It is intended that project outcomes will also contribute towards building public support and accelerating the pace of climate action, while also ensuring climate justice principles are adhered to⁵.

1.2. Background

The CLIMATUDE workplan comprised four separate but interlinked knowledge creation packages of work. The first is concerned with exploring how much society understands and how much it trusts climate science. The second is focused on understanding the perceptions that the public have of government policy and messaging around climate change. The third assesses citizens' engagement with, and understanding of, climate science and the level of trust they have in public institutions to deliver on climate strategies that are both fair and equitable. The fourth, building on this citizen engagement, aims to co-develop a better understanding of the relationship people have with their public institutions (especially in the context of climate change).

³ As demonstrated by the strong presence of science and technology in the Irish economy coupled with the above average performance of Irish students in science and mathematics (OECD 2023), and the high level of trust afforded to scientists on climate change by Irish people (O'Mahony *et al.*, 2024).

⁴ As Upton Sinclair (1994, 1934) said '*It is difficult to get a man to understand something, when his salary depends upon his not understanding it*'.

⁵ CLIMATUDE will also include a consideration of nature of climate justice both as the general system of ethics and how it might be implemented.

This report is the first of two planned outputs from the second of these work packages, 'Public perceptions of government policy and messaging on climate change'. It involves 'capturing a picture' of the climate change policy and regulatory landscape in Ireland. This report will be complemented by a subsequent companion report on the levels of trust in Irish public institutions with regards to climate change.

1.3. Structure of the document

The report is divided into six sections as outlined below.

The initial section, *Introduction*, describes the foundation of the project and provides background and context to the work undertaken.

The second section, *Methodology*, outlines the desk-based research approach adopted for this consideration of climate change policy and regulation across different scales.

The third section, *Policy and Regulatory Context*, comprises an introduction to the context of climate change the policy & regulation landscape within Ireland.

The next section, *Irish Climate Policy Domain*, provides an analysis of the principal actors and players involved in Irish climate policy.

The fifth section, *Irish climate policies and regulations*, provides an overview of Irish climate-related public policy describing the relevant regulations, guidelines and plans and outlining the engagement of citizens with environmental policy in Ireland.

Finally, the last section, *Conclusions*, summarise the report's findings and clarifying their meaning for the project as a whole.

2. Methodology

2.1. Introduction

The work presented in this report emerged from a programme of in-depth, desk-based research involving a detailed review of the literature on climate change policy and regulation across different scales. It began with an initial scoping exercise to identify the key drivers that impact climate policy development in Ireland, but also across Europe and internationally. This work included the identification and analysis of data from existing literature from academic research databases. Other sources that proved useful included what is termed ‘grey literature’ (comprising of contemporary political and legal themes) and reports from non-governmental organisations (NGOs), national and local governments, as well as supranational bodies like the European Union institutions.

Developing a solid understanding of existing research (derived from different knowledge sources, applicable theories, and practice-based analyses already in the public domain) is foundational to developing new knowledges and should be considered a core component of the research process. To do this, the authors reviewed the growing body of literature on climate policy and government legislation relating to Ireland, but also all associated international treaties and legislative frameworks that inform national policy. The selection criteria and subsequent collating of data was followed by a rigorous thematic analysis to identify common themes in the literature. Thematic analysis is widely used in qualitative research as it allows for the identifying, analysing, organising, describing, and reporting on the key themes from the data being investigated (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Nowell *et al.*, 2017). While Castleberry and Nolen (2018) note it does need to be rigorous in its application, when done correctly it is also very useful for encoding qualitative information, *e.g.*, translating the languages of both qualitative and quantitative research into a coherent mix-methods approach (Boyatzis, 1998).

2.2. The Literature Review

“Qualitative and quantitative reviews do not form a dichotomy. Rather, literature reviews exist on a continuum from highly qualitative (with little mention of statistics or research methods) to highly quantitative (with the final synthesis based on the mathematical averaging of results across various studies reported by different researchers).”

Pan, 2017, p. 3

Conducting a thorough literature review is essential to the research process, whether to synthesise existing research or to contextualise one’s own analysis of the data they have collected (Cooper, 1998). An expected outcome should be the development of new knowledge and insights or at least the confirming of an existing position on a given topic (Schryen *et al.*, 2021; Torraco, 2005). It is

impossible for a researcher to adequately understand the topic they are researching without one (Hart, 2018). However, despite its recognised importance Onwuegbuzie and Freis (2016) note the literature review can sometimes be relegated to being considered as undervalued preliminary part, albeit necessary, of the research process. This is a mistake. Taking an open-minded appraisal of existing literature is essential to undertaking a critically informed plan of future research activities and the literature review very much serves as a research method in its own right.

The literature conducted for this report served two purposes. Firstly, to assess the policy & regulation landscape in Ireland with regards to the climate crisis as set out for task 3.1 in the project's workplan. The task was to identify key legislation and notable policy innovations that have occurred in Ireland over recent decades, including any notable drivers and barriers to citizen participation, and to present these in a coherent and useful presentation in the report. The second purpose was to act as a foundational framework for a further, deeper exploration of the literature, which will inform Deliverable 3.2's reporting on the relative success or otherwise of these policies to change people's behaviour around energy use and consumption relative to national carbon emissions targets. This was achieved using Dunphy *et al.*'s (2021, p. 10) approach to assessing available literature through '*the familiar iterative process of searching, reading, annotating, organising, summarising, analysing, and finally synthesising*' findings.

Through this process we can begin to get a deeper understanding of the research topic and develop a more informed state of the art with regards to current scientific thinking *etc.* The following sections outline the initial results from this effort.

3. Policy and Regulatory Context

3.1. Introduction

Climate Change is in many ways the defining issue of our age. This is particularly evident within the public policy domain with new legislation often underscored by, or at least acknowledging, the factoring in of climate considerations to the policy cycle.

A primary goal of Ireland's climate policy is achieving a carbon-neutral, climate resilient economy by 2050 underscored by an initial target of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 51% by 2030. Two key pillars of this transition to net-zero include the Government of Ireland's **Climate Action Plan 2021**⁶, which is supported by the **Climate Action and Low Carbon Development (Amendment) Act 2021**⁷. Together, they provide a framework for achieving these targets through a set of legally binding carbon

⁶ <https://www.gov.ie/en/department-of-climate-energy-and-the-environment/publications/climate-action-plan-2021/>

⁷ <https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2021/act/32/section/15/enacted/en/html>

budgets and sectoral emissions ceilings. They also aspire to reversing recent sharp declines in biodiversity and habitat loss and linking them within a combined strategy and align with the objectives of the European Commission's 2020 **European Green Deal**⁸.

3.2. Overview of Influence on Environmental Policy in Ireland

There is a diverse selection of cultural, social, political and economic factors which influence Irish environmental policy.

Cultural Identity

Cultural identity plays a significant role in influencing Irish environmental policy. Ireland has both a global image and a national cultural identity as 'green'. A perception of Ireland exists in the popular consciousness—developed through a complex interplay of aesthetic and cultural factors—of a pastoral society, where citizens have an intimate material connection to the land. Despite the fact that this image of Ireland has been contested and complicated by seismic change in the economic and social makeup of the country as well as by changes to the material and ecological realities of Ireland's agrarian economy since the establishment of the state in 1922, it persists in popular culture and is perennially reinvigorated by both national discourse and branding. As Slevin and Barry (2024, p.29) note however *"prevailing perceptions of Ireland's 'Green' standing obscures its actual environmental performance and the country's climate reputation oscillates between 'laggard' and 'leader'."*

Fáilte Ireland⁹ has since the 1990s sought to present Ireland as a picturesque escape from modernity, a place at odds with a technologically advanced Western society *"visual representations picture Irish natives 'as predominantly working in agriculture and implicitly suggest that an organic relationship between people and their natural environment is to be found in Ireland"* (Johnson, 1999, p.191). While this branding is primarily intended for international markets, it is also aimed at stimulating domestic tourism. The greatest success story of Irish tourism in recent years has been 'The Wild Atlantic Way Campaign *"drives €3 billion in revenue per year"* (Hilliard, 2024). The campaign promotes Ireland's West coast as a holiday destination almost exclusively on the basis of its natural beauty. The aesthetic and cultural value of the region's ecology is both enshrined and perpetuated by the campaign.

We might also consider the extent to which cultural relationships to nature are enshrined by social and historic factors. While Irish culture is not monolithic, as a postcolonial nation, Ireland has historically (in part at least) defined itself in opposition to Britain. In the wake of colonisation Ireland's

⁸ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

⁹ Ireland's Tourism Development Agency

poverty was by necessity was rebranded as heritage, which stood in contrast to England's perceived industrialised sophistication. As Kelli Ann Costa notes, "*the battered and backward but breathtaking landscape of Ireland was re-imagined as the traditional and well-preserved*" (2009, p.41). This adoption of a picturesque aesthetic and of a deindustrialised society as a signifier of not only postcolonial resistance but of an emerging national identity remains central to Irish national relationships to ecology.

It is notable that many of the most globally recognisable images of Ireland are of rural Ireland. These images, generated across art, photography, film and media are typically ones where agriculture plays — to a greater or lesser extent — an aesthetic, thematic or narrative role. It is also of note that the systems of management and socio-economic engagement with the rural ecologies represented in these images are typically at odds with mainstream contemporary agricultural land management practises in Ireland. That is, there is a notable absence of technologically sophisticated, large-scale, productivist methods of agriculture.

While cultural texts which represent Ireland's natural and built environments are produced by both national and international actors and are intended for diverse audiences, there is an underlying impulse both international and self-reflexive to continually reinvigorate representations of Ireland as a place where the effects of climate change are not apparent or cannot be reasonably accommodated by the internal logic of the text. This would seem to suggest an unwillingness to address climate issues but arguably is more likely reflective of an enduring national and international perception of Ireland as a place in harmony with nature. The images of Ireland which have become culturally significant nationally and marketable internationally and emblematic internationally are dependent on the maintenance and sustainable development of Ireland's natural environment.

Attitudinal Factors

There is widespread consensus in Irish society around the threat posed by climate change as well as the need to address climate change and mitigate the risks it poses. The *Climate Change in the Irish Mind* report states that "90% of [Irish] people say the country has a responsibility to act on climate change" and a large majority of people surveyed (85%) are "worried" about climate change (O'Mahony *et al.*, 2024, p.3). This engagement with and awareness of climate change has the potential to influence voter and consumer behaviours, which can in turn, potentially impact climate change policy. The *Climate Change in the Irish Mind* report also reveals that most Irish people support climate action with 79% of respondents stating that climate change should be a very high or high priority for government (O'Mahony *et al.*, 2024, p.3). This national attitudinal relationship to climate change also influences the degree to which policy is accepted and how it is perceived by the public.

Political Factors

Ireland's political landscape presents a diverse series of factors which have the potential to influence climate change policy.

Ireland as a Democracy

Ireland's democratic status is an important consideration when attempting to appreciate influences on climate change policy. While eco-authoritarian thinkers would argue that the short-term nature of democratically elected governments fails to encompass the kind of long-term planning needed to effect and oversee real action in climate change policy, it is worth considering the degree to which a citizenry who are mobilised around and educated on issues of climate change will reflect that in their voting. As Adachi *et al.* note:

"People's political preferences are not fixed; they do change and can be changed. If the preferences of the citizenry become the embodiment of an ethics of responsibility to future generations, and accordingly, if central political agents such as politicians, bureaucrats and journalists opt to, or are forced to, change their political preferences, then the possibility for the adoption and implementation of far-sighted public policies will surely be increased in democracies."

Adachi *et al.*, 2024, p.122

European Union Membership

Among the influences on Ireland's climate change policy is the state's EU membership, which through a series of legally binding agreements and directives, ties Ireland into specific actions intended to mitigate the effects of climate change and transition Ireland towards a carbon neutral economy. Ireland's EU membership also ensures a degree of oversight over climate change policy. Failure to comply by Irish governments can result in fines and penalties. Criminal activity against the environment can also be tried in European courts. This overarching framework however is subject to criticism. In 2020 Barbara Mariani, senior policy officer for climate at the European Environmental Bureau (EEB), argued that *"evidence points towards the need to increase the EU [emissions reduction] target to at least 65%"* (Anastasio, 2020). Criticisms aside, it is notable that much of Ireland's environmental and climate change policies are transposed from and responding to European Union directives. It could also be argued that the 'cover' provided by EU policies enabled Irish governments to enact environmental regulation that would have been unpopular amongst the electorate.

Fossil Fuel Lobbying

Another factor which influences policymaking is lobbying by fossil fuel companies. Analysis by the *Kick Big Polluters Out* coalition found that at least 1,773 fossil fuel lobbyists had been granted access to COP29 talks (Kick Big Polluters Out, 2024). The risks posed by fossil fuel lobbying are pertinent to discussions of Ireland's climate change policy. In 2021 Fuels for Ireland, (formerly the Irish Petroleum Industry Association) a fossil fuel lobbying group, launched a complaint against the Irish state in response to its efforts to redirect a 2 cent per litre fuel levy to the Climate Action Fund (now part of state taxation policy). The group argued that other energy sources like gas and electricity from non-renewable sources were not subject to the same levy and that this constituted “[unfair] targeting of their members” (Fleet Transport, no date). A Bill intended to “prohibit advertising of fossil fuels and fossil fuel undertakings and to provide for certain exemptions; to prohibit sponsorship by fossil fuel products and fossil fuel undertakings” (Houses of the Oireachtas, 2025), titled Fossil Fuel Products (Control of Advertising and Sponsorship) was sponsored by Senator Lynn Boylan in 2024, however the Bill lapsed with the dissolution of the 33rd Dáil in advanced of the General Election in November 2024.

Government Will

The will of government to appropriately oversee climate policy also plays a factor in its development. While the whip system in Irish politics ensure that party members are obliged to vote with their party during Dáil debates, the degree to which governments will fully commit to oversight and enactment of these policies is not always clear. For example, Kerry politician Michael Healy-Rae TD¹⁰, who has gone on public record to state his interest in allowing forestry on Irish Peatlands¹¹ (Flynn, 2025) was appointed Minister for Agriculture, Food, Fisheries and the Marine in 2025 and as such has responsibility for Irish forestry initiatives. While it is unclear if the direction of the department will change, but it speaks to a certain idiosyncrasy of government (in Ireland and elsewhere) whereby ministers with professed opposition to policies for climate action and biodiversity protection may be placed in positions of oversight for these policies.

The Russia-Ukraine War

The ongoing Russia-Ukraine war is likely to impact future climate change policy in Ireland, though how it will do so it not yet clear. Maslin *et al.* (2023, p.11) note that the effects of the war on renewable

¹⁰ Teachta Dála, a member of Dáil Éireann (the lower house of the Irish Parliament, or Oireachtas)

¹¹ A move at odds with current national biodiversity and afforestation policy.

energy are already observable as “*the EU is moving away from Russian gas as quickly as possible, having pledged to double the instillation of renewable energy this decade*”.

Media

The impact of media on climate change policy should be considered. Grossman states that:

“...media effect on policy making is [...] at best indirect: Parties or candidates promote specific issues and policies during campaigns, and voters express support for the party whose policy agenda they prefer through their vote; if voting is influenced by media, then media influence policies by influencing the vote decision.”

Grossman, 2022, p.445

Indirect influence however is not lack of influence, and the impacts of media on voters and policy makers are important considerations. In 2024 an Oireachtas Joint Committee on Environment & Climate Action heard a report on the role of media and communications, particularly the impact and regulation of advertising that promotes fossil fuels (Joint Committee on Environment & Climate Action, 2024). The Committee acknowledged “*the critical importance of communication, media and advertising in generating behavioural impact on the scale required to meaningfully lower emissions and tackle climate change*” (*Ibid.*, p.8).

Traditional News Media

The EPA’s 2024 *Climate Change in Irish Media* report highlights the specific mechanisms by which influence is generated through news media. Of particular relevance are the report’s highlighting of the effects of episodic reporting and media framing. Episodic media coverage focuses on individual events or cases, often highlighting personal stories and specific incidents without overarching context. It differs from thematic coverage, which presents issues within a broader social or political context. Episodic reporting serves to compartmentalise and fragment wider climate issues, for example coverage of environmental issues may increase during periods of extreme weather but following this, the news cycle will move on and “*climate change is often pushed down the news agenda*” (Culloty *et al.*, 2024, p.3). Another factor to consider is the specific ‘framing’ of climate change in news media. The Climate Change in Irish Media report notes that:

“The media framing of climate change is both episodic and thematic, with episodic framing linked to a particular newsworthy event, such as a conference or summit, and thematic framing taking the form of a conceptual characterisation. Much of the existing literature has been concerned with thematic framing. Some of the major conceptual frames

identified in the literature include risk and fear; scientific certainty/scepticism; climate change impacts and consequences; collective identity for response; and climate responsibility and justice.”

Culloty *et al.*, 2024, p.5

Social Media

The advent of social media has brought a diversity of potential impacts to bear on climate change policy in Ireland. The influence of social media on climate change policy remains significantly under researched. However, drawing on existing research and on the observed influences of social media more broadly we can infer certain potential impacts. A widely publicised and frequently cited concern around social media is the potential effects of misinformation. The *Climate Change in Irish Media* report states:

“On social media, climate change discourses are led by distinct influential groups, including the mainstream media, the NGO sector and the non-governmental sector. Although these groups dominate engagement during the high-profile UN Conference of the Parties, the presence of citizen-led and organised scepticism is also notable. In particular, we find a high volume of content linking to the US-based Heartland Institute indicating the capacity of ‘fake news’ and misinformation to infiltrate online platforms.”

Culloty *et al.*, 2024, p.ix

It is also worth highlighting the potential positive impacts of social media on public engagement and thus the development of climate policy. Influencers whose platforms are built on climate advocacy or sustainability have the potential to become online spaces where sustained coverage of environmental issues takes place. The individuals also serve as mobilisers for public engagement and collective action (Schäfer, 2025). It should be noted that due to the algorithmic nature of social media platforms, this kind of environmentally engaged content is not likely to reach all users, it will instead reach users who deliberately seek it out or demonstrate engagement with these issues. Kotkaniemi *et al.* (2024, p.362) posit “*policy process research should apply caution when assuming correspondence between online and offline relationships, as distinct policy contestation arenas differ in how policy influence is formed*”.

Representation of Climate Change

Perhaps the most impactful, though least researched of media influences on policy development is the specific representation of climate change in media.

“Visual representations speak to the “cultural imagination” of climate change and include those images accompanying news reports, as well as environmental and ecological representations in art, photography, literature and film [...] visual depictions of climate change are dominated by representations of causes and consequences.”

Culloty *et al.*, 2024, p.6

Contemporary media displays a concerted lack of representations of solutions, futures, or eco-imaginaries, where a new system of relationship to environment outside of our contemporary crisis moment can be explored and contested through the imaginative freedom offered by cultural production. The kind of representation highlighted in the EPA’s report, tend to focus on “*polar bears and smokestacks*” images which, through over-saturation, run the risk of stymieing collective action and indeed ambitious policy through a sense of hopelessness and a lack of political and social imagination.

Economic Factors

An Adaptable Economy

There is a diversity of conflicting and interrelated economic factors which have the potential to shape and influence climate change policy in Ireland. Ireland’s economy is a knowledge-based service economy and deeply embedded within systems of international trade and investment. Ireland’s low tax/high skill economic model that combines a highly educated workforce with a comparatively low corporate tax rate (12.5%)¹² has historically spurred economic growth and attracted investment, particularly in the technology sector. Wang *et al.* have highlighted the adaptability and flexibility of knowledge-based economies which they note “*typically exhibit dynamic regulatory frameworks that enable prompt adaptations to changing economic and environmental conditions*” (Wang, 2023, p.5). They argue that these economies are well-placed to adopt “*environmentally friendly technologies and sustainable strategies*” compared to agricultural or industrial economies which prioritise natural resources and labour. The specific economic landscape of Ireland means that it is, in theory well placed to efficiently engage with policies of sustainable development and to make a just transition to a green economy.

¹² Although this context will change somewhat with the adoption of the OECD global base erosion (GloBE) model rules, which establish a 15% global minimum effective tax rate for large multinational enterprises with annual revenues exceeding €750 million.

Foreign Direct Investment

The adaptability of this economic framework is complicated by several factors. First is the over-reliance on foreign direct investment from large multinational corporations. According to a report published by the Central Statistics Office in 2024:

“In 2021, there were 12,436 foreign-owned multinational enterprises in Ireland, which represented just 3.4% of total enterprises in the Irish Business Economy, but they generated 72% of both total turnover (€798.8bn) and total GVA (€266.7bn). They employed 28.2% of the total number of persons employed in the Business Economy. These foreign-owned multinationals were 26.1% EU owned and 73.9% non-EU owned.”

Central Statistics Office, 2024

The Irish State’s neoliberal disposition has a direct impact on its policy orientation (Slevin & Barry, p.35). The degree to which Irish economic growth is reliant on multinational corporations is in itself a contentious issue. These enterprise’s continued investment in the state is not guaranteed. More than this however is the commitment of these enterprises to sustainable development goals both in Ireland and beyond. Companies such as Diageo, X (formerly Twitter), and Unilever are among some of the companies with bases in Ireland which in 2025 were delisted from The Science Based Targets initiative’s list of net zero commitments in 2024 (Darley, 2025). Regardless of how multinational enterprises conduct their operations in Ireland, they are not necessarily subject to the same laws elsewhere. It should be recognised that climate change is a global issue and Ireland’s sustainable development goals and policies are sometimes undermined by economic growth fostered by enterprises which further degrade and endanger the environment on a global scale. Another factor likely to influence climate change policy is the willingness of firms to accept these policies. A 2024 report from the Central Bank of Ireland reveals that:

“The green transition may reduce productivity growth in the short term, as increased production costs (e.g. due to carbon taxes) coincide with a requirement to invest in technologies that may not increase firms’ productive capacity relative to the more carbon intensive methods currently in use.”

Conefrey et al., 2024, p.30

In spite of this, the 2024 EY State of Sustainability report saw:

“81% of respondents report[ing] a heightened focus on sustainability within their organisations [...] a 19% increase from the previous survey in 2022 (Dennis, 2024). This

increased focus on sustainability is potentially bolstered by the Green Transition Fund (an EU funded initiative, part of Ireland’s National Recovery and Resilience Plan). The aim of the fund is to ‘accelerate the decarbonisation of Irish enterprise.’”

Údarás na Gaeltachta, n.d.

Cost of Noncompliance

The significant cost of failing to comply with legally binding commitments to carbon neutrality is also a significant influence on policy development. A 2023 report from the Irish Fiscal Advisory Council estimates the costs of noncompliance “at an annual average of about €0.35 billion up to 2030, when costs rise to €0.7 billion (0.2% of GNI*)” (Casey and Carrol, 2023, p.3). Economic and climate justice are intimately linked, and a failure to adequately legislate for climate change would have an adverse effect on Ireland’s economic stability, the social mobility and economic security of its citizens. Another related cost of noncompliance is the cost associated with purchasing carbon quotes to avoid facing legal proceedings in the European Court of Justice. A 2025 EPA report, *Ireland’s Greenhouse Gas Emissions Projections 2024–2055*, reveals that Ireland is unlikely to achieve its 2030 climate obligations and will likely need to purchase carbon quotas.

Language

In a comparative analysis of the Irish and Norwegian gas and oil extraction systems Slevin notes that:

“In contrast to Ireland, Norway’s approach has consistently been underpinned by a belief that the resources ultimately belong to the people of the country who should receive maximum benefits from hydro-carbon exploitation. Yet, despite its rhetoric of public ownership, Norway is also subject to pressures from the global capitalist economy.”

Slevin, 2016, p.156

Slevin’s acknowledgement of the role of rhetoric in developing a public perception around Norwegian hydro-carbon exploitation is useful, because it clarifies the role of language in shaping public policy as well as in perceptions of those policies. A frequency analysis of climate-related language in the Climate Action Plan 2021 document reveals the twelve more frequently used words / phrases:

Climate	Emissions	Renewable	People
Sector	Energy	Targets	Just Transition
Carbon	Ireland	Community	Society

Figure 1 Illustrated frequency of the 12 key climate related words most commonly used in the Climate Action Plan 2021

The dominant thematic focus of the document is on emission and climate change mitigation processes, consequently energy and renewable energy appear frequently also. The word ‘citizens’ appears by contrast only 11 times. ‘Future generations’ appears twice. This shows a significant disparity in the thematic focus given to technical responses to climate change and the sociological dimensions of climate change. This disparity speaks to the specific focus of the plan, that is wide-ranging technological change through innovation. Gold notes that:

“The Irish climate movement is part of the much bigger story of the global climate movement, which is itself embedded within the contested spaces of global civil society. The idea of a ‘global civil society’, whilst contested, is generally viewed as the place ‘outside’ the market and the state defined by voluntary association amongst citizens (Schaefer et al. 2013). The realm of civil society is where citizens meet, discuss, form associations and mobilise on issues of concern.”

Gold, 2020, p.278

The report points to a certain lack of ideological engagement with Irish society except as a container for industry and economy, rather than acknowledging society’s role as a living and complex collection

of social, cultural, gender, ethnic, religious and ideological factors that combine to effect change or stymie progress. Instead, the document aligns Irish society along industrial-oriented narratives with recourse to words like ‘sector’ and ‘stakeholder’. This type of packaging and prioritising of focus exposes the neoliberal biases that predominate Ireland’s official narratives and highlights the extent to which there is a real disconnect from what should be a meaningful reckoning with what is, at present, very much an unsustainable status quo. Recent decades in Irish economic policy have seen a bias towards fostering (economic) growth through highly globalised, free market processes and foreign direct investment, rather than through the establishment of indigenous industries or investing more deeply in state-owned assets. While seemingly positioning itself as advocating for promoting change, this is very much at a surface level. Rather pointing to the long-term systemic change that is needed, we can observe here the groundwork for the same systems of hierarchical, highly centralised power and administration that have engendered the climate crisis and social inequalities we are already facing.

3.3. International Climate Change Policy

Beginnings of International Policy and the Kyoto Protocol

Though the scientific community was coalescing around the issue for considerably earlier, international actors and policymakers began to galvanise around the issue of anthropogenically driven climate change from the 1980s onwards. This political awareness has been attributed to an “*upturn in the global temperature record*” (Maslin *et al.*, 2023). While there had been research into and an awareness of the effects of GHGs among the scientific community since the 1960s (and the beginning of international policy intervention, with the Club of Rome publishing their report *The Limits to Growth* in 1972 (Meadows *et al.*, 1972) this research was ‘rediscovered’ in the 1980s and began to meaningfully enter public discourse as a problem which required solving. The first major international political and policy intervention into climate change in this period was the United Nations’ 1987 report *Our Common Future* (WCED, 1987). In 1988 the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) was established and by 1990. Climate change remained present within public and political discourse into the 1990s, though its effects and influence were disputed, notably by fossil fuel companies (van den Hove *et al.*, 2002). Despite this, in 1992 The United Nations convened the Rio Earth Summit¹³, which was intended to assist member states with efforts to cooperate on issues relating to sustainability and the protecting of the world’s environment. Maslin *et al.* (2023, p.2) note the significance of the event, which:

¹³ Formally referred to as the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED).

“...led to the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development, the local, national and global sustainability initiative called Agenda 21 and Forest Principles. It was also the first time that parties could sign up to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) that the UN set to negotiate limits to global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The conferences also encouraged the parties to join the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification and the Convention on Biological Diversity.”

The UNFCCC currently operates under the proviso of ‘agreement by consensus’, which unfortunately opens the doors for countries to stall or even impede any decision they do not favour (Maslin *et al.*, 2023). The first policy to be enacted by the UNFCCC was the Kyoto Protocol in 1997. For the first time, signatories (particularly from developed countries) were subject to legally binding emission targets. Following its ratification by Russia, the Protocol entered into force on 16 February 2005, though several industrialised countries have refused to ratify it, including the United States and Australia (and Canada withdrawing from it in 2012).

The Paris Agreement on Climate Change

The next major development in international climate policy came in 2016 with the Paris Agreement on Climate Change. The Paris Agreement is the first universal, legally binding global climate agreement adopted by 195 Parties at the UN Climate Change Conference (COP21) on 12 December 2015 and entered into force on 4 November 2016. The treaty covers key topics including climate change mitigation, adaptation, and finance and saw the establishment of legally binding commitments to keep the rise of global surface temperature well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels. No small task, given this would require a global emissions cut of roughly 50% by 2030.

Geopolitical Controversies

Subsequent COPs have not necessarily translated directly to policy, however the decisions taken at COPs carry significant political and socio-economic weight, with the conferences often becoming staging grounds for negotiating complex geopolitical disputes. A primary example of this is the COP15 summit which took place in Copenhagen, Denmark in December 2008. COP15 widely expected to produce effective and ambitious dialogue on climate action. However, this expectation went unrealised due to a series of controversies. The first among them was an exclusion of NGOs from proceedings. NGOs were denied access to the conference venue due to a lack of sufficient room. In addition to this, Danish negotiators were unprepared for the conference due to the pre-conference negotiators being replaced by the Danish Prime Minister’s team during the conference leading to the controversial leaking of ‘The Danish Text’. What was essentially a draft agreement that was eventually

presented as the "Copenhagen Accord", countries were expected to adopt the document at the plenary session. The appearance of a new text in the middle of an ongoing conference led to significant disputes between nations. This uneasy landscape saw Chinese and Indian delegates take a stance, whereby they encouraged so-called 'developing' nations to seek an agreement that suited their interests rather than those of so called 'developed' nations. These tensions were further compounded by US engagement. As Maslin *et al.* (2023, p.4) note:

"Barack Obama arrived only two days before the end of the conference. He was fully aware that the US Senate and the House of Representatives would not agree to binding targets. The US negotiators were also fully aware of how China and India were blocking all progress. So Barack Obama convened a meeting with the BASIC (Brazil, South Africa, India and China) countries, excluding all other UN nations, and created the Copenhagen Accord. This recognised the scientific case for keeping temperature rises below 2°C, but did not contain a target baseline, nor commitments for reducing emissions to achieve it. Earlier proposals that would have aimed to limit average temperature rise to 1.5°C and cut CO2 emissions by 80% by 2050 were dropped. This was because all mention of a 1.5°C rise was continually blocked by China. The resulting agreement was non-binding and countries could provide their own voluntary targets. It was also made clear that any country that signed up to the Copenhagen Accord was also effectively stepping out of the Kyoto Protocol, hence the US was able to move away from the binding targets of the Kyoto Protocol, which should have been enforced until 2012. A weak voluntary commitment approach was adopted. The Bolivian delegation summed up the way the Copenhagen Accord was reached: 'anti-democratic, anti-transparent and unacceptable'."

The complexity of the international geopolitical context of COP and the degree to which taking a progressive stance on climate change could carry a material or political cost for members was made evident when, following COP15, a subsequent Wikileaks revelation showed that "US aid funding to Bolivia and Ecuador was reduced because of their opposition to the Copenhagen Accord" (Maslin *et al.*, 2023, p.5). The intervening decade has seen increased uncertainty as to the capability of nations to achieve this target in addition to attempts by US President Donald Trump to withdraw from the Agreement. The COP summits themselves have also faced criticism particular from NGOs, see *e.g.*, the following comment from Jasper Inventor, Head of COP29 Greenpeace Delegation (Greenpeace 2024):

"The agreed finance goal is woefully inadequate and overshadowed by the level of despair and scale of action needed. The best and worst of multilateralism saw isolated blockers and difficult talks stymie change before a deal was brokered at the death knell. Our true

opponents are the fossil fuel merchants of despair and reckless nature destroyers who hide snugly behind every government's low climate ambition. Their lobbyists must be disallowed, and leaders need to summon the courage to get on the right side of history."

In addition to this, as mentioned earlier the *Kick Big Polluters Out* coalition found that at least 1,773 fossil fuel lobbyists had been granted access to COP29 talks, which undoubtedly serves to undermine the integrity of the institution as well as impacting progress towards effective carbon reduction goals (Kick Big Polluters Out, 2024).

3.4. European Climate Change Policy

Europe: The Kyoto Protocol and The Paris Agreement

The European Union has been an active driver in the development of international climate policies since the Rio Summit. At the time, the European Union sent a delegation not only as a proactive move to ensure oversight and widespread adoption of all agreements by its member states, but to advocate for those member states. The European Union signed the Kyoto Protocol on the 29th April 1998.

"In December 2001 the Laeken European Council confirmed that the Union wanted to see the Kyoto Protocol enter into force ahead of the Johannesburg world summit on sustainable development (26 August – 4 September 2002). To that end, this Decision approved the Protocol on behalf of the Community. The Member States were to coordinate their action to deposit their instruments of ratification at the same time as the Community, and as far as possible by 1 June 2002."

European Union, 2011

The European Union ratified the Kyoto Protocol in 2002; under European policy frameworks:

"States which were members of the EU before 2004 must collectively reduce their greenhouse gas emissions by 8 % between 2008 and 2012. Member States which joined the EU after that date undertake to reduce their emissions by 8 %, with the exception of Poland and Hungary (6 %), and Malta and Cyprus."

European Union, 2011

The Paris Agreement was subsequently ratified by all EU member states on the 5th of October 2016. Under the agreement EU countries are required to: (1) meet the long-term goal of keeping the increase in global average temperature to well below 2°C, compared to pre-industrial levels; (2) pursue extra efforts to limit the increase to 1.5°C; prepare and apply national action plans (Intended

Nationally Determined Contributions) to meet these targets; (3) report to each other and to the public on the progress they are making on their commitments; from 2023, conduct a planet-wide stocktake every 5 years with international partners, to set further targets based on scientific evidence and the results achieved; (4) take measures to deal with the impact of climate change that is already unavoidable; and (5) provide practical and financial support to developing countries, to help them adapt to climate change (European Union, 2016).

While the Agreement has been ratified by the European Union – also prompting the development of a suite of legislation under the Green Deal programme – critics have pointed out that allowing members to determine their own individual contribution significantly compromises the effectiveness of the Agreement due to non-compliance and stalling on the part of some member states (Kakar, 2024). The European Commission, however, does have the power to launch infringement procedures against member states that are not complying with EU law.

The European Climate Law and The European Green New Deal

In 2019, the European Commission launched *The European Green Deal* which was a culmination of efforts aimed at "transforming the EU into a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy" (European Commission, 2024a).

"The European Climate Law writes into law the goal set out in the European Green Deal for Europe's economy and society to become climate-neutral by 2050. The law also sets the intermediate target of reducing net greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by at least 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels. Climate neutrality by 2050 means achieving net zero GHG emissions for EU Member States as a whole, mainly by cutting emissions, investing in clean technologies, and protecting the environment. The law aims to ensure that all EU policies contribute to this goal and that all sectors of the economy and society play their part."

European Commission, 2024b

While this law and policy programme are dictated at EU level, as with the Paris Agreement, it is expected that individual Member States will develop their own policy responses. The long-term strategies should be consistent with each Member State's integrated National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) for the period 2021–30. The governance regulation required Member States to submit their first national long-term strategies to the Commission by 1 January 2020. The next strategies are due by 1 January 2029 and every 10 years thereafter. Member States should, where necessary, update their strategies every five years. A broad analysis of European environmental policy reveals that:

“In its process of climate neutrality governance, the EU primarily employs “Regulatory Instruments” and “Social Instruments”, with less frequent utilization of “Economic and Financial Instruments”. Firstly, the EU leverages “Regulatory Instruments” to provide unambiguous policy direction, employing mandatory measures to steer businesses and individuals towards more environmentally friendly and sustainable production and lifestyles. Secondly, the EU utilizes a diverse array of “Social Instruments”, employing guiding policy measures to advance the climate neutrality governance process. Through these “Social Instruments”, the EU elevates public awareness and concern regarding climate change and climate neutrality governance, enhancing public engagement in climate action and accelerating the climate neutrality governance process. Thirdly, in its deployment of “Economic and Financial Instruments”, the EU prioritizes guiding capital flows, diversifying policy tools, and emphasizing the utilization of market mechanisms.”

Wang et al., 2024, p.23

3.5. Ireland’s Relationship to International Climate Change Policy

Ireland has had a presence at international climate talks since the Rio Earth Summit, which was attended by Ministers from the Department for the Environment and the Department of Foreign Affairs. While there, delegates signed both the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). Ireland would ratify the Convention on Biological Diversity in 2002. Ireland would later go on to sign the Kyoto Protocol, (which would be ratified under EU law in 2002) and the Paris Agreement (ratified under EU law in 2016). This process will be explored in the next section.

Ireland and European Climate Change Policy

Ireland’s relationship to European climate policy is not an easy one. Ireland has historically had numerous failures in complying with environmental law referred to the ECJ. In 2019:

“The European Commission opened 38 cases against Ireland for infringements of EU law last year, [...] More than half of all infringement proceedings in 2019 were related to the late transposition of EU directives, although the number went down slightly (from 419 cases in 2018 to 406 in 2019).”

Law Society Gazette, 2020

In 2023 Ireland was summoned to the European Court of Justice due to:

“its persistent failure to meet its obligations under the Habitats Directive and properly designate Special Areas of Conservation (SACs), more than five years after the deadline for this has expired (more than 10 years for some sites). 423 sites were due to be designated as SACs and some of the claims brought against Ireland are that 149 of these sites do not have sufficient conservation measures in place for the species and habitats for which they’re designated and 230 of the sites have no conservation measures in place at all.”

Fair Seas, 2023

And in 2024:

“... Ireland, Bulgaria, Spain, Malta, Portugal and Slovakia to the Court of Justice of the European Union for failure to finalise the revision of their river basin management plans, as required under the Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC) and/or of their flood risk management plans as required under the Floods Directive (Directive 2007/60/EC)”

European Commission, 2024c

These breaches can be contextualised by considering Ireland’s relationship to the European Union. Though support for the EU continues to be strong in Ireland, there has been somewhat of a transactional dimension Ireland’s membership of the EU (Torney & O’Gorman, 2019). This transactional relationship has seen Ireland benefit from and become deeply embedded within European structures. Though, arguably, Europe has not necessarily become embedded in Ireland. The specific psychogeographic effect of Ireland as island as well as its postcolonial status, have historically enforced a sense of distance in Irish public perceptions of Europe. Ireland’s specific economic context also complicates its relationship to policy. As Glynn *et al.* (2019) reveal, Ireland is:

*“...unique in the EU with a large share (>30%) of GHG emissions from agriculture. The reduced scale of mitigation options in agriculture – both in terms of the production efficiencies currently available and potential future options in research and development (Chiodi *et al.*, 2016; Kuramochi *et al.*, 2018) – places a disproportionately high burden on the energy system to decarbonize relative to other member states. [...] Ireland’s electricity network is the smallest national synchronous power system in the EU. It has the highest share of variable renewable electricity supply on a synchronous power system and is leading globally in wind energy integration.”*

Glynn *et al.*, 2019, p.30)

Additionally, the neoliberal status of Ireland's economy frequently undermines or is asynchronous with climate action. As such, "Ireland struggles to achieve GHG reductions, despite the state's climate change legislation and policies. Concentrating on supply-side climate policy, this article examines key issues hampering Ireland's ability to reconcile its climate ambitious with policy and practice" (Slevin & Barry, p.29). A recent Environmental Protection Agency report reveals that Ireland is significantly off-track in meeting its 2030 climate obligations (EPA, 2025). Ireland has previously been obliged to purchase €121million on carbon credits due to its failure to reach its emissions targets in 2019 and will very likely need to do so again. Indeed, writing in the Irish Times newspaper in May 2025, Pat Leahy suggests the state could face financial penalties totalling as much as €28 billion if it does not achieve its greenhouse gas emissions targets by 2030 (Leahy, 2025). These repeated failures to achieves legally binding targets as well as the numerous infringements issues raised by the ECJ point to a determinedly lax approach to European policy implementation in Ireland. Ireland has, it has been argued:

"...remained immune from pressures of convergence resulting from EU membership. Despite good progress in some areas such as renewable energy deployment, in terms of altering the trajectory of Ireland's GHG emissions, the EU framework has had remarkably little impact on Ireland's performance."

Torney and O' Gorman 2019, p.576

Despite this, the European Union has attempted to facilitate Ireland's just transition with €84.5 million worth of funding coming from the Just Transition Mechanism (part of the European Green Deal Investment Plan) "primarily focused on the economic transition of the Midlands region, which has been heavily impacted by the phasing out of peat extraction" (European Commission, 2024d). A broad analysis of Ireland's relationship to European climate policy reveals a country that with the support and incentive of funding structures and legally binding agreements is outwardly well-placed to achieve its GHG reduction targets. On closer analysis however a more contentious situation emerges, wherein complex interrelations between national industry and a lack of political initiative result in a failure to comply with policy or to meaningfully innovate national solutions.

Ireland's Territorial Just Transition Plan

A policy and €84.5 million investment package were passed in 2022 focusing on the Midlands region which stand to be most impacted by the end of peat extraction. The plan centres on three priorities:

1. Generating employment through investment in the local economies.

2. Restoration and rehabilitation of degraded peatlands and repurposing of industrial heritage assets.
3. Providing former peat communities with “smart and sustainable” mobility options.

The use of the term “Just Transition” closely resembles early demands for just transitions of labour movements whose industries faced threats from environmental regulation – with a distinct focus on retraining and reskilling. This contrasts more recent use of just transitions and wider discussions on energy and justice, which hold broader systemic and social focuses beyond employment opportunities. This is partially reflected by a mapping of the most frequently used words in the report, showing a notable focus on terms like “economic” and “development” over terms such as “public” and “social” as shown in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Most frequently used meaningful words in the Territorial Just Transition Plan (excluding references, footnotes, punctuation, and common stop words like “the” “and” etc.). Generated using ChatGPT

4. Irish Climate Policy Domain

4.1. Introduction

In considering the key actors involved in climate action in Ireland, there tends to be four main ‘influence clusters’ in Irish environmental policy and are usually presented in terms of (1) Governance, (2) Business, (3) Energy and Research, (4) Environmental Coalition and what can be defined as a ‘heterogenous set of actors’ (Wagner and Ylä-Anttila, 2018). This breakdown continues to be reflected in recent policy. Wagner and Ylä-Anttila (2018) present a network analysis of survey data from those organisations involved in the national climate policy process. Their findings point to there being several institutionally important, economically powerful organisations (most notably from the agricultural sector) in addition to key government parties looking to ensure their preferences were reflected in any subsequent legislation. As a result, they contend that the legislation excluded any strong binding emission reductions targets, which saw Ireland differentiating from similar laws developed in other European countries (*Ibid.*). Having said that, those organisations in favour of stronger regulation did go on to form a coalition to advocate their shared position, though this coalition largely failed in achieving its objectives. While their study specially focuses on advocacy coalitions, it is a useful resource for analysing the engagement and influence of specific groups in the drafting of national legislation.

4.2. Organisational engagement in national legislative processes

In subsequent Climate Action reports, many of the groups Wagner and Ylä-Anttila (2018) identify are no longer mentioned, which can be explained in several ways. Firstly, O’Mahony *et al.* (2024) report that NGOs are less trusted as a source of information around climate change than others such as scientists, Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), educators, and even family and friends (see Figure 3 and Figure 4 below). There has also been a trend of government bodies shifting away from engaging directly with these groups since this early effort, towards a more collective engagement. In this context it is worth noting that many of these groups (Birdwatch Ireland, An Taisce, Voice, Friends of the Earth, *etc.*) while operating independently are also members of an advocacy consortium, the Environmental Pillar. Formed by government decision in 2009, this consortium is the advocacy arm of the Irish Environmental Network, providing a space for the various national environmental non-governmental organisations (NGOs) to come together and work towards developing and then advancing policy solutions that represent the views of those working in the Irish environmental sector.

Neither the Environmental Pillar nor any of its member organisations – with the exception of An Taisce (Ireland’s National Trust) – are mentioned in the government’s 2025 Climate Action Plan (DCEE, 2025). This most recent climate action plan is the third statutory annual update to the Climate Action Plan

(Government of Ireland, 2025). This could be seen as somewhat of an indicator reflecting an ongoing trend of exclusion for environmental NGOs in policy development at the national scale. Though engagement may manifest elsewhere and will require further analysis, which will be presented in subsequent reports. It is also worth noting the degree to which public consultation is cited and sought in policy development. Much of this consultation is conducted under the auspices of the National Dialogue on Climate Action.

Figure 3: Levels of trust across different cohorts of Irish society - Part 1 (data sourced from O’Mahony et al., 2024)

Figure 4: Levels of trust across different cohorts of Irish society - Part 2 (data sourced from O'Mahony et al., 2024)

The Climate Change Advisory Council (CCAC)¹⁴ also has a notable mention in the 2021 Climate Action Plan and their recommendations are also considered in the 2025 Plan. The council published its annual

¹⁴ The Climate Change Advisory Council (CCAC) has been in existence since January 2016 and operates under section 8 of the Climate Action and Low-Carbon Development Act 2015. The remit of CCAC is to provide independent advice and recommendations to the government, through the Minister for Climate, Energy and the Environment on how best to respond to the impact of climate change. In accordance with the Act, the CCAC provides annual and periodic reports regarding Ireland's progress in achieving its national policy goals and greenhouse gas emissions targets agreed by the European Union. In May 2021, the Department of Climate, Environment and Energy along with other relevant Government Departments and Agencies, signed a Memorandum of Understanding with the CCAC. The Memorandum facilitates greater sharing of data, modelling and analysis to promote further transparency and collaboration in evidence-based climate policy making including the development of Carbon Budgets. The Climate Action and Low Carbon Development (Amendment) Act 2021 makes provision for the CCAC to prepare and propose carbon budgets ensuring that they are consistent with the national climate objective and have regard to the relevant rules applied by the European Union. Section 9 of the Climate Action and Low Carbon Development (Amendment) Act 2021 provides for two distinct Regulations, which are required to: provide clarity to the CCAC on how to determine their proposals for carbon budgets; and provide clarity to the CCAC on how to calculate and account for emissions and removals. The first of these, Climate Action and Low Carbon Development Act 2015 (Greenhouse Gas Emissions) Regulations 2021, received Government approval on 12 October 2021.

report on the most recent developments in relation to Ireland’s changing climate in March 2025 (a month before the publication of the government’s Climate Action Plan). A key recommendation included calls for the government to establish “a national climate damage register to monitor the impacts of extreme events in a uniform and standardised manner” and to “provide the necessary funding and support to sustain and improve the national climate observation system” (2025, p.x). In response, the government’s indicated that “the overall and sector-specific recommendations in the CCAC annual review are addressed in the relevant chapters of this Climate Action Plan, and have been incorporated into policies, measures, and actions in so far as it is possible to do so” (p.46).

Groups mentioned specifically in the government’s 2025 Climate Action Report, who are either defined as having a specific role in informing or implementing the government’s climate policy are presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1 Groups identified in Climate Action report 2025 as playing a role in climate policy

Governance bodies	Business, Energy and Research	Environmental	Other
<i>Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)</i>	Research Ireland	An Taisce	NI Dept. of Agriculture, Environment & Rural Affairs
<i>Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI)</i>	<i>ESB Networks</i>	<i>National Dialogue on Climate Action *</i>	<i>National Parks and Wildlife Service</i>
<i>Department of Agriculture, Food and Marine</i>	BiOrbic	Global Alliance for Green and Gender Action (GAGGA)	<i>Teagasc</i>
<i>Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage</i>	VistaMilk	<i>Youth Climate Assembly*</i>	<i>Gaelic Athletic Association (GAA)</i>
Department of Climate, Energy and Environment	<i>Fáilte Ireland</i>	Climate Change Advisory Council*	
<i>National Transport Authority</i>	<i>Bord na Móna</i>		
<i>Transport Infrastructure Ireland</i>	<i>Coillte</i>		

Note: Groups who stretch the definition of Environment/Governance Body are indicated with *, while groups who previously appear in the 2021 Climate Action Plan are indicated with italics

4.3. Citizen participation

Participation of citizens in the policy process is increasingly recognised as an important element of decision-making within modern democracies. This is generally viewed as beneficial for the political system, especially in terms of fostering trust. Changes in levels of citizen participation can act as a measure of the overall quality, robustness and general health of decision-making (Dunphy & Lennon, 2021). When public bodies talk of citizen participation, it is important to appreciate what they (truly) mean. Sherry Arnstein’s seminal article ‘*A Ladder of Citizen Participation*’ (1969) identified three broad categories of participation, namely, non-participation, tokenism and citizen power, which are subdivided into eight levels as shown in Figure 5:

Figure 5: Arnstein’s ladder of participation

The lowest two levels, Manipulation and Therapy are non-participative. Citizens are involved in the process so as to be educated or engineered into providing their support. Informing, the third level, forms the first real step towards participation, as at this level the citizen is genuinely informed of his or her rights, options and responsibilities, but the communication is unidirectional. The next level Consulting includes a degree of two-way communication but is still mostly for show. Placation, the fifth level of the ladder, represents the point where the citizen begins to have some level of influence, although the powerholders are still in primary control and the main purpose of the participatory process is to soothe the public into complacency. The next level is Partnership, which involves a redistribution of power resulting from negotiations between the powerholders and the citizens. Arnstein stresses that such negotiations are generally initiated by citizens rather than by powerholders. The highest level of

participation is Citizen Control. Here, citizens demand the power to govern a programme and negotiate conditions under which it can be changed. While citizen engagement at even the lowest levels has some value, it is really from levels 5-6 that true participatory policymaking can take place.

Citizen participation in policy making is driven by an underlying democratic culture, transparent governance processes, civic identity, strong civil society, and accessible participation mechanisms. At a basic level citizens participate in democratic processes to influence decisions, protect their rights and ensure accountability. Motivation for citizen participation in policymaking tends to be attributed to self-interest and/or a sense of responsibility – supported an idea of a collective identity. Antonini *et al.* (2015, p. 133) suggest that motivation for such participation “*may not be solely ascribed to the role of rewards/costs expectancy of citizens’ participation, suggesting that willingness to participate in policymaking could be influenced by other variables.*” Their work found that there was a three-way interplay between **collective identity, cost & benefits, and trust** in determining the willingness of citizens to engage with the policy process. They noted the centrality of trust (both in governments and in processes), point out that when trust is low neither collective identity nor perceived benefits are likely to result in willingness to participate.

The drivers for public bodies to include citizens in decision-making is summarised by Smith, Stirling and Berkhout’s (2005, p. 220) argument that “*under a normative view, participation is just the right thing to do. From an instrumental perspective, it is a better way to achieve particular ends. In substantive terms, it leads to better ends.*” This argument asserts that it is only right that citizens who have a stake in the decisions should be involved, it also contends that it can be a good means of achieving particular goals, and finally it makes the point that citizen participation will improve the quality of decision-making through the incorporation of diverse knowledge and values. Moriarty and Daly (2023) suggest that citizen involvement and participation can serve to increase ambition for climate action and argue by making policy making more inclusive that social trust is enhanced, contributing to successful outcomes. They also posit that higher levels of trust coupled with inclusive participatory processes can reduce inequalities, when noting a somewhat virtuous cycle that equal treatment acts to include social trust and enabling inclusive and participatory policy processes.

Morisson & Ferrario (2025) identify four principal barriers to citizens being active participants in policymaking and implementation processes. They point out the importance of **accessibility**, with many groups marginalised and excluded from participatory processes through for example language difference, digital divides, and logistical constraints. The **risk of tokenism** is also seen as a factor, with superficial perfunctory processes leading to both poor outcomes and loss of trust. **Resource constraints**, limited funding and other resources meaning reduced capacity to implement

participatory policy processes. Finally they note potential reluctance to share decision-making power, such **bureaucratic resistance** serves to undermine engagement efforts. While arguably encompassed in the aforementioned resource constraints, it is worthwhile to explicitly mention **skills deficit** as a barrier to participation. Abas *et al.* (2025) observe that “(s)killed practitioners are critical to the success of participation as they can facilitate the process, maintain a good relationship with citizens, and generate better results.”

OECD (2025) identified eight types of challenges to the effective design and implementation of citizen participation processes. These challenges (which encompass the above barriers) include:

- **Trust:** Many citizens do not have faith in governments nor in the outcomes of participatory processes.
- **Impact:** difficulty in evaluating impact, poor accountability, and Inconsistent feedback can impede the impact of participation.
- **Institutional:** Disconnection from decision-making reduces impact of participation. Lack of awareness or incentives within public bodies can result in poor buy-in.
- **Exclusion:** disregard of marginalised groups, lack of accommodation for those with additional needs, and overly technical and/or bureaucratic language can be exclusionary.
- **Design:** overly complex, time consuming and/or non-interesting process can result in reduced participation.
- **Isolation:** gap (real or not) between process and the public can hinder legitimacy and impact.
- **Integrity:** vulnerability to undue influence by vested interests will impact outcomes
- **Resources:** lack of adequate capacities and resources will hinder participatory processes.

5. Irish climate policies and regulations

5.1. Introduction

A primary goal of Ireland's climate policy is achieving a carbon-neutral, climate resilient economy by 2050 underscored by an initial target of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 51% by 2030. Two key pillars of this transition to net-zero include the Government of Ireland's **Climate Action Plan 2021**¹⁵, which is supported by the **Climate Action and Low Carbon Development (Amendment) Act 2021**¹⁶. Together, they provide a framework for achieving these targets through a set of legally binding carbon

¹⁵ <https://www.gov.ie/en/department-of-climate-energy-and-the-environment/publications/climate-action-plan-2021/>

¹⁶ <https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2021/act/32/section/15/enacted/en/html>

budgets and sectoral emissions ceilings. They also aspire to reversing recent sharp declines in biodiversity and habitat loss and linking them within a combined strategy and align with the objectives of the **European Green Deal**¹⁷.

Climate Action Plans

Ireland's Climate Action Plans are a series of annual statutory updates starting from 2019, outlining the country's strategy to achieve a 51% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 and reaching the target of net-zero GHG emissions by 2050. Launched in June 2019, Ireland's first Climate Action Plan, Climate Action Plan 2019 (CAP19), outlined an ambitious course of action towards responding to the many intersecting drivers and wide-ranging impacts the climate crisis is already beginning to have on Ireland's environment, its society and economy, and with regards to its existing natural resource. Since then, the Climate Action Plan has been updated and now is its fifth iteration (CAP2021, CAP2023, CAP2024, CAP2025) with measures and actions further refined to deliver the carbon budgets and sectoral emissions ceilings set out the roadmap.

5.2. Overview of Influence on Environmental Policy in Ireland

The following list presents the key legislative to consider when assessing Ireland Climate and environmental policy landscape:

- **Future Ireland Fund and Infrastructure, Climate and Nature Fund Act 2024**¹⁸ is intended “to finance investment associated with delivering on Ireland’s climate and nature goals, and to provide for countercyclical capital expenditure in the event of an economic or fiscal downturn.”¹⁹
- **Petroleum and Other Minerals Development (Prohibition of Onshore Hydraulic Fracturing) Act 2017**²⁰ prohibits the “*exploration and extraction of petroleum from shale rock, tight sands and coal seams in the Irish onshore and Ireland's internal waters.*” The prohibition does not extend to offshore hydraulic fracturing.
- **Fossil Fuel Divestment Act 2018**²¹ “commits Ireland's national treasury to divesting its Strategic Investment Fund entirely from fossil fuels within five years after the passage of the law.”²² Under this legislation Ireland’s national treasury is required to divest from fossil fuel

¹⁷ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

¹⁸ <https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2024/act/16/enacted/en/html> [<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2024/act/16/enacted/en/html>]

¹⁹ National Treasury Management Agency (NTMA) (2025) Infrastructure, Climate and Nature Fund. [online] <https://www.ntma.ie/business-areas/future-ireland-funds/infrastructure-climate-and-nature-fund>

²⁰ <https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2017/act/15/section/1/enacted/en/html>

²¹ <https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2018/act/29/enacted/en/html>

²² Grantham Research Institute, n.d. Fossil Fuel Divestment Act 2018. Climate Change Laws of the World [online] https://climate-laws.org/document/fossil-fuel-divestment-act-2018_eaba?l=ireland&c=laws

undertakings “as soon as practicable” and must “ensure that its assets are not directly invested in a fossil fuel undertaking unless such an indirect investment has less than 15 percent of its assets invested in a fossil fuel undertaking.” The law does however allow for investment by the national treasury in fossil fuel undertakings which are “(1) the transition to decarbonisation, (2) the implementation of Ireland’s climate change obligations, or (3) the government’s climate change policy objectives”²³. The national treasury is required to list investments made under these exemptions publicly.

- **Maritime Area Planning Act 2021**²⁴ is intended to expedite and enable Ireland’s decarbonisation through the streamlining of offshore energy development. It reforms previous consent regimes legislating for “a single consent principle, i.e., one State consent (Maritime Area Consent) to enable occupation of the Maritime Area and one development consent (planning permission), with a single environmental assessment”²⁵.

Government Strategies and Frameworks

- **Biodiversity Climate Change Sectoral Adaptation Plan**²⁶ published in 2019 and developed under Ireland’s National Adaptation Framework aims to “protect biodiversity from the impacts of climate change and to conserve and manage ecosystems so that they deliver services that increase the adaptive capacity of people and biodiversity while also contributing to climate change mitigation” (p.4). The plan acknowledges the need to integrate an awareness of Ireland critically threatened biodiversity into the national response to the climate crisis. The plan builds on the **National Biodiversity Action Plan (2017 - 2021)**²⁷ with the aim of “improving sustainable agriculture and fisheries, better soil and land management and, most urgently, the restoration of natural systems” (p.3). The Biodiversity Climate Change Sectoral Adaptation Plan acknowledges that Ireland’s biodiversity continues to be threatened by climate change and also recognises biodiversity as a tool in mitigating and reacting to the effects of climate change.
- **National Adaptation Framework**²⁸, published in 2024, it is the second iteration of a statutory National Adaptation Framework first published in 2018 in line with requirements set out in the Climate Action and Low Carbon Development Act (2015). The framework

²³ Grantham Research Institute, n.d. Fossil Fuel Divestment Act 2018. Climate Change Laws of the World [online] https://climate-laws.org/document/fossil-fuel-divestment-act-2018_eaba?l=ireland&c=laws

²⁴ <https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2021/act/50/enacted/en/html>

²⁵ Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage. (2021, 17 December) Maritime Area Planning Bill 2021 passes through all stages of the Oireachtas. Press release. Available at: gov.ie

²⁶ Department of Culture, Heritage and the Gaeltacht. (2019) Biodiversity Climate Change Sectoral Adaptation Plan.: <https://www.npws.ie/sites/default/files/publications/pdf/Biodiversity-Climate-Change-Sectoral-Adaptation-Plan.pdf>

²⁷ National Parks & Wildlife Service. (2017) *National Biodiversity Action Plan*.

<https://www.npws.ie/sites/default/files/publications/pdf/National%20Biodiversity%20Action%20Plan%20English.pdf>

²⁸ Department of Climate, Energy and the Environment. (2024) National Adaptation Framework. Available at: <https://www.gov.ie/en/department-of-climate-energy-and-the-environment/publications/national-adaptation-framework-naf/>

requires Local Authorities to “*prepare adaptation strategies for their administrative areas to reduce the vulnerability of the state to the negative effects of climate change and to avail of any positive effects that may occur*” (p.22).

- **Project Ireland 2040 National Planning Framework**²⁹ is a high-level strategic plan intended to “guide public and private investment, to create and promote opportunities [...] and to protect and enhance [Ireland’s] environment” (p.10). The framework makes specific references to addressing climate change, citing “*Resource Efficiency and Transition to a Low Carbon Economy; Protecting, Conserving and Enhancing Our Natural Capital and Creating a Clean Environment for a Healthy Society*” (p.117) as key focus areas.

5.3. Policy Engagement in Ireland

The engagement of Irish citizens with environmental policy is influenced by broad range of social, political and cultural factors. Engagement here is taken to mean the ability to influence, be aware of and to engage critically with policy.

Personal Values and Demographic Factors

Irish citizens’ engagement with environmental policy is profoundly influenced by demographic and personal political factors. Bourke *et al.* (2024) recognise this impact highlighting the effect age, social dominance orientation and gender have on attitudes to climate change and the environment more generally. Their people-centred research into climate change attitudes revealed numerous:

“Differences in climate change attitudes emerge across different demographic groups. The gender effect is the most consistent – women show higher levels of belief and concern about climate change. Younger people may also show higher levels of belief; however, these findings were less clear.”

Bourke *et al.*, 2024, p.64

In addition:

“Social dominance orientation - a preference for hierarchy within society and the domination of higher-status groups over lower-status groups - was found to be associated with greater climate change denial. Across European countries, individuals who hold a such attitudes and show intolerance of particular social groups, including migrant and LGBT groups, were more likely to show more climate change scepticism.”

²⁹ Government of Ireland. (2018) Project Ireland 2040: National Planning Framework. Available at: <https://www.npf.ie/wp-content/uploads/Project-Ireland-2040-NPF.pdf>

Bourke *et al.*, 2024, p.11

There are other factors discussed in the study, though the effects and influence of factors such as political orientation and level of educational attainment on climate change belief is less clear. The personal and political have the potential to meaningful influence a citizen's policy engagement.

Voting System and Elections

The most immediate way in which Irish citizens can engage with, and influence, government policy is through exercising their democratic right to vote. Ireland's electoral system uses proportional representation – single transferrable vote (PR-STV). PR-STV is a candidate-based system. This means voters can choose to vote for as many, or as few candidates as they like, in order of their preference (Electoral Commission, no date). A voters first preference, their number one vote, takes precedence and is always counted. Their second and subsequent votes will be counted if their first-choice candidate is eliminated or elected with a surplus. This is the transfer system. Within Ireland's electoral system, several candidates are typically elected to represent each constituency. This allows for a broad spread of opinions on and priorities towards potential policies to emerge from a constituency, though not necessarily consensus. One potential issue, with the potential to influence policy that arises from the PR-STV system, is a tendency towards localism in Irish politics. An Oireachtas report from 2013 states that:

“An excessive focus on local issues in Irish politics is blamed for weakening parliament's capacity to hold the Government to account and scrutinise legislation. This localism has been attributed, in part, to the weak system of local government.”

Oireachtas Library & Research Service, 2013

The report also notes that this focus on local constituency issues over national topics can have additional negative consequences, with nationally minded individuals often deterred from entering politics, leading to poor national planning as legislators strive to deliver services in their own areas at the significant cost to national planning goals. While the effects of climate change are undoubtedly felt at a local level, the expectation that elected representatives, or TDs³⁰, should privilege local issues means that TDs are unlikely to campaign on national issues during elections. As an example, a brief analysis of the elected TDs from across the political spectrum, for Cork North Central constituency reveals the following key priorities:

³⁰ A Teachta Dála (TD) is a member of Dáil Éireann, the lower house of the Oireachtas (parliament of Ireland).

- Colm Burke TD (Fine Gael³¹) – To deliver an elective hospital and Primary Care Centres locally, accelerate the construction of new homes across Cork; support farmers and families in rural Ireland; to provide resources for law enforcement, social support and a Day Centre for those affected by homelessness and addiction.³²
- Thomas Gould TD (Sinn Féin³³) – Housing (in particular, the eradication of social housing waiting lists vacancies, dereliction and people being locked out of home ownership).³⁴
- Ken O’Flynn TD (Independent Ireland³⁵) – Immigration control; healthcare (particularly issues faced by individuals having to access healthcare in Northern Ireland); urban issues.³⁶
- Eoghan Kenny TD (Labour³⁷) – The construction of a relief road in his local area; investment in a hospital in his local area; rural transport; “direct investment in our education system, primary, post primary, special schools and third level institutions across Cork.”³⁸
- Pádraig O’Sullivan (Fianna Fáil³⁹) – Flood relief works; autism spectrum disorder education supports; local housing & community investment.⁴⁰

The absence of environmental issues here points to a sense among (prospective) public representatives and the voting public that these issues are not immediate concerns or at the very least are not issues which are within the remit of TDs to resolve. It also indicates that these issues are potentially not a priority when casting their vote. It also means that there is potentially little oversight in implementing national policies at a local level.

Ireland’s Current Government

The Irish government is a coalition government led by Fianna Fáil (centre/centre-right) and Fine Gael (centre-right/liberal conservative) and supported by the Regional Independent Group⁴¹. In Fianna Fáil

³¹ Fine Gael describes itself as a party of the progressive centre; generally considered to be centre/centre-right with liberal conservative & Christian democracy wings. Affiliated at EU Level to European People’s Party (EPP).

³² Facebook post, Colm Burke. www.facebook.com/ColmBurkeTD/videos/446097784889033/ (Accessed: 20-Aug-25).

³³ Sinn Féin is a left-wing nationalist and democratic socialist political party, considered to be centre-left to left. Affiliated at the EU Level to Unified European Left (UEL).

³⁴ Thomas Gould profile. <https://www.sinnfein.ie/representatives/thomas-gould-td/> (Accessed: 20-Aug-25).

³⁵ Independent Ireland is a right-wing party, affiliated at EU level to the European Democratic Party (EDP).

³⁶ Ken O’Flynn profile. <https://www.independentireland.ie/kenoflynn> (Accessed: 20-Aug-25).

³⁷ The Labour Party is a centre-left social democratic Irish political party, at the EU level it is affiliated to the Party of European Socialists (PES).

³⁸ Eoghan Kenny profile. <https://labour.ie/people/eoghan-kenny/> (Accessed: 20-Aug-25).

³⁹ Fianna Fáil is a centre to centre-right political party in Ireland, at the EU level it is affiliated to the Alliance of Liberals and Democrats for Europe (ALDE).

⁴⁰ Pádraig O’Sullivan party profile. <https://www.fiannafail.ie/tds/padraig-osullivan/> (Accessed: 20-Aug-25).

⁴¹ An informal coalition of Irish Independent TDs formed to represent rural and constituency-specific interests in the Dáil. The group focuses on local issues, disability services, and regional development

and Fine Gael's election manifesto's they set out statements on climate change. Fianna Fáil argues for *"Sustained action to tackle the climate crisis; to decarbonise the economy; and harness the digital and AI revolution to deliver effective and modern public services and to grow the economy"*. Fine Gael state that the party is *"committed to making Ireland resilient to climate change, recognising that achieving our climate goals is essential to our future economic success"*⁴² (p.42). A more complex issue is understanding the political stance of the Regional Independent Group. The group is composed of several independent, non-party politicians who have agreed to support and work with the Fianna Fáil–Fine Gael coalition, though they do not necessarily share common goals or ideologies. Chief Executive of Friends of the Earth, Oisín Coghlan has stated that:

"We need to hear from the regional independents where they stand on climate action. Three of them voted against the climate law and three of them voted in favour. Who is speaking for them on climate in the government formation talks and what are they saying? Is it Michael Lowry or Sean Canney who voted for and against respectively."

Friends of the Earth, 2024

Coghlan also called for the outgoing and incoming Taoiseach and Tánaiste⁴³ to comment on their commitment to *"uphold the climate law and progress a just transition to a zero pollution Ireland no matter who they are in Government with"*. Coghlan's comment reflects the degree to which there is a potential in Irish politics to water down commitments to climate action in order not to lose the support of coalition members who are not aligned with these goals. There is the potential for TDs and political parties to prioritise access to government over legally binding environmental targets.

Voter Turnout, Voter Demographics and Government Timelines

Voter turnout at the 2024 General Election was low at 59.7% – down from 62.9% in the 2020 General Election. Though there is evidence to suggest that the *"electoral register includes many surplus records, and this overestimation has significant implications for turnout estimates"* (Däubler, 2025). It is also worth noting however that evidence suggests that:

"...voter turnout is especially low among younger populations and in deprived urban communities with low rates of home ownership. Rural dwellers, particularly farmers, are more likely to vote. Increased education results in higher turnout, but is less of a factor"

⁴² Fine Gael General Election 2024 Manifesto: Securing Your Future
<https://www.finegael.ie/app/uploads/2024/11/Fine-Gael-General-Election-2024-Manifesto.pdf>

⁴³ Head and Deputy Head of government of Ireland

than age. [there is also evidence to suggest that local candidates garner] greater support, particularly in rural areas.”

Gerba, 2024, p.15

It is also worth considering individuals and communities excluded from voting in Ireland. The Traveller, Roma and Gypsy communities in Ireland for example, have faced significant barriers to accessing the democratic process and are not represented in the demographic makeup of Dáil Éireann’s elected representatives (Minceirs Whiden, no date).

People under eighteen are also excluded from the democratic process and it could be argued that it is difficult for ‘future generation thinking’ to manifest through the democratic process without the insight of generations who will feel the effects of climate change most keenly. The lifetime of a given government also impacts the goals and deliverables which governments and elected officials will commit to. In Ireland elections are typically held every five years. Politicians may choose to prioritise short-term goals and deliverables which can be measured materially by the citizenry (infrastructure, constitutional reform, economic reform), even a disengaged citizenry rather than long-term, less tangible goals such as carbon reduction. In this respect it is worth highlighting exit polls taken during the 2024 general elections:

“In response to a question on individual voters’ views of the Government’s approach to climate change, 51% said ‘the current Government has not gone far enough’. A fifth (20%) said the current Government has gone ‘too far’ and 29% that the current Government’s actions are about right”.

Ó Cionnaith, 2024

Citizens Assemblies and Deliberative Democracy

Another means through which the public are facilitated to engage with environmental policy is through the Citizen’s Assembly⁴⁴. The Citizens Assembly which ran from 2016 to 2018 considered the following five topics: (1). The Eighth Amendment of the Constitution (regarding regulation of Termination of Pregnancy), (2). How we best respond to the challenges and opportunities of an aging population, (3). Fixed term parliaments, (4). The manner in which referenda are held, and (5). How the state can make Ireland a leader in tackling climate change. As such, they placed:

⁴⁴ The Irish Citizens’ Assembly (2016-18) was a successor to, and closely followed the model of, the 2012-14 Irish Constitutional Convention

“...the citizen at the heart of important legal and policy issues facing Irish society. With the benefit of expert, impartial and factual advice the 100 citizen Members considered the topics below. Their conclusions formed the basis of a number of reports and recommendations that were submitted to the Houses of the Oireachtas for further debate by our elected representatives.”

Citizens' Assembly, 2016a

During its lifetime, that iteration of the Citizens Assembly was requested to make recommendations on several issues. Among them *“How the state can make Ireland a leader in tackling climate change?”*. Hogan (2018) argues that:

“As a deliberative forum, [the Citizens' Assembly] allows for submissions from the wider public and interest groups which feed into the decision-making process by the members of the Assembly. Its conclusions will have to be drawn from expert evidence, which steers the deliberation away from interest bargaining. The format of the Citizens' Assembly ensures that the recommendations to the Oireachtas will be the product of balanced debate, and that the narrative surrounding reform is less likely to be dominated by inaccuracy or misinformation by interest groups.”

Informed recommendations on climate change from the Irish citizenry are to be welcomed and there is also *“a long track record of Citizens' Assembly recommendations having a significant impact on policy, legislation and constitutional reform”* (Citizens' Assembly, 2016b). It is worth acknowledging that the recommendations made by the Assembly are not legally binding. As a result, there is no accountability required on the part of elected officials in relation to the recommendations, beyond a requirement to ‘respond’ to them. While the potential of this mechanism of citizen engagement to effect constitutional reform can be exemplified by the 2015 Marriage Referendum (2015) and the 2018 Abortion Referendum, Naomi O’Leary (2019) writing in *POLITICO* observed that while the Assembly was:

“...synonymous with its work on abortion. Less well known is the fact that it examined a portfolio of issues, including voting reform and climate change. Many of its recommendations on these have gone nowhere yet.”

Media Coverage and Dissemination

The episodic nature of environmental reporting in Ireland has been discussed elsewhere in this report. This episodic approach has a profound impact and citizen engagement with the issue of climate

change and their engagement with and understanding of the policies intended to tackle it. As the Ireland's national broadcaster, RTÉ has a specific and central role in disseminating information to the public and in responding to climate change policy. In 2023, the broadcaster released RTÉ on Climate 2023-2025, a document, responding to the Government's Climate Act 2021. In this document, RTÉ highlighted their progress and further commitment to tackling climate issues and informing the public:

"In an industry first, RTÉ became one of 12 broadcasters and streamers to have signed up to The Climate Content Pledge. The signatories – including the BBC, Channel 4, ITV, RTÉ, S4C and Sky – are committing to using their content to help audiences understand what tackling climate change might mean for them, as well as inspire and inform sustainable choices. RTÉ is also one of 19 broadcasters from across Europe to have launched a climate action campaign. RTÉ plays a trusted and important role in informing Irish citizens and in shaping national debate. While RTÉ is mindful of the need to do more, coverage of climate change and environmental issues is central to RTÉ News and Current Affairs coverage and across many other different types of programming."

RTÉ, 2023 p.34

Though there has been criticism of RTÉ's climate coverage in recent years, further research is required to identify what, if any, impact the procedures, goals and approaches outlined in RTÉ on Climate 2023-2025⁴⁵ will have. The government's most recent strategies and approaches to implementing the Climate Act are set out in the Climate Action Plan 2025⁴⁶. The document is available to the public and can be accessed from the gov.ie website. The report however runs to 187 pages and while the language used is clear and concise, it is not necessarily accessible or appealing to the lay reader. There is however an infographic booklet⁴⁷ which can be accessed from the same webpage on gov.ie, which significantly condenses the information in the original Climate Action Plan from 2021 and is more clearly aimed at a lay reader.

Interest Groups

Groups representing business and professional interests, NGOs and citizens groups can also engage with and effect change to policy through lobbying.

⁴⁵ For further analysis of the 'RTÉ on Climate 2023-2025', refer to D3.2.

⁴⁶ Climate Action Plan 2025, Government of Ireland
https://assets.gov.ie/static/documents/c491032e/DECC_Climate_Action_Plan_2025_Main_Report_-_Final_Web.pdf

⁴⁷ <https://assets.gov.ie/static/documents/climate-action-plan-2021-infographic-booklet-e8395eb4-8def-4e1e-b28a-fe54ebd5b334.pdf>

“Interest groups play a central role in Irish society by theoretically acting as a conduit between citizens and the government (...) Interest groups are, however, much more than simple conduits and lobby in the expectation that they will receive some tangible benefits for their efforts. In that context, the access and expectation such groups have to, and on, Irish policymakers can be of great significance for policy outcomes in the Irish state.”

(Murphy, 2017)

In the context of climate policy, NGOs have the power to galvanise public opinion behind an issue as well as the power and access to the government institutions with the potential to resolve or mitigate them. NGOs can be oriented towards specific political, economic or cultural aims. However, the political, economic or ideological aims of these groups need not necessarily align with those of an elected government in order to influence policy. We might consider for example the actions of Focus Ireland, an Irish homelessness charity who have successfully lobbied the Irish government in the development of a tenant-in-situ scheme. This tenant-in-situ scheme is designed to prevent individuals from becoming homeless should their rental residence be sold. As such it aligns with the goals of the NGO to lobby government to legislate in favour of their issue.

6. Conclusions

The primary aim of this report is to give an overview of the contemporary environmental policy landscape in Ireland, particularly in relation to climate. Rather than simply listing the leading drivers and barriers to the successful implementation of these policies, the report goes further by analysing the narratives framing these policies and the wider governance landscape in Ireland. We posit that this context is valuable both to policy development and climate research more broadly. Subsequently, the report lays out the groundwork for research through mapping the complex and interconnected factors that have the power to shape both policy and public perceptions of policy.

The report charts the influence of Ireland’s changing cultural identity, noting the pervasive myth of Ireland as a “green”, pastoral country and notes that this perception of Ireland as being a country in harmony with nature can obstruct policy implementation. The report also assesses the various political factors impacting Irish environmental policy — namely Government will, democratic systems, Ireland’s EU membership, the rise of global instability and the lobbying power of fossil fuel companies. In addition to the economic considerations, the report highlights other factors that have the power to influence policy, including the adaptability of Ireland’s economy, its neoliberal leanings, and the influence of foreign direct investment.

An analysis was conducted of the language used in the Irish Government's Climate Action Plan (2021). The aim was to identify the dominant thematic forces within the document to better understand how the policy would be perceived by the public but equally to see where and to what extent policy makers had considered the role of public opinion and values. Our analysis revealed a relative absence of socio-cultural dimensions. We posit that multi-scalar systemic change across society requires the inclusion of a significant socio-cultural dimension in policy.

The report then offered an overview of environmental policy, beginning by charting the emergence of cohesive international efforts to address climate change. We then moved to a discussion of three key policy documents framing Ireland's environmental (and climate) policy landscape, that emerged from the Rio Earth Summit, the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement. These landmark moments in climate change policy are contextualised as events deeply entangled with geopolitical tensions, contestations around international trade, and the relational workings of interdependent states. Having established this framing, we discussed the translation of policy stemming from the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement into the environmental policy of the European Union. Finally, we situated Ireland's climate policy landscape within the wider European and international contexts. Here, we tracked the ways in which the implementation of environmental policy in Ireland has diverged from or aligned with European Union directives. Our research suggests that despite a well-established presence at international and European climate talks, Ireland's relationship with European climate policy is complex and frequently fractious — marked by infringements of European policy. Ireland's relationship to EU climate policy therefore is far from straightforward. This we attributed to a diversity of factors, among them: Ireland's somewhat transactional relationship with the European Union, its neoliberal orientation, its status as an island, and the ensuing relative difficulty of decarbonisation when compared to other EU member states.

Following this, we moved into an overview of the key actors influencing the development of Irish environmental policy. Drawing on Wagner and Ylä-Anttila's (2018) research, we identified four main "influence clusters" in Irish environmental policy development. We highlighted the waning influence of environmental NGOs, this we attributed to an increasingly concentrated sphere of influence within government departments, advisory groups, state bodies and semi-state bodies. Ireland's key climate legislation was analysed with a view to identifying the current infrastructure of climate policy. This legislative map will be employed going forward as a reference document to support further research and analysis into policy and public perceptions of policy.

We concluded this report with a broad analysis of Irish people's engagement with environmental policy. Here we go beyond flagging the drivers and barriers to success and move into an analysis of

the socio-cultural narratives underpinning policy success and failures. We began by assessing the influence of personal values and demographic characteristics. Our research found that factors such as age, social dominance orientation and gender can shape individual attitudes towards climate change. We also note that Ireland's voting system operates under a system of proportional representation using a single transferable vote (PR-STV). We suggested that this system can foster a tendency towards "localism" in Irish politics.

To demonstrate this, we presented a case study, wherein we presented the manifestos of elected TDs for the Cork North Central constituency. We posited that the absence of climate issues in these manifestos suggests climate change is often framed as outside the remit of TDs and that environmental issues may not be perceived as a voter priority. We also argue that it suggests a potential lack of oversight from elected officials in the local implementation of climate policy. Further to this we considered the policies and track record of Ireland's current government. We analysed the manifestos of Fianna Fáil and Fine Gael and found that both parties present economic growth and sustainability and transition as deeply intertwined. We noted also that there is the potential within Irish politics to dilute commitments to climate action due to an inability to complete projects within the lifespan of a given government's term. They can also potentially be diluted to maintain coalition support due to the disparate and diffuse climate stances adopted by the Regional Independents group. Finally, we considered the influence of citizen's assemblies and the media in shaping policy and public attitudes around climate issues.

In this report we have developed a broad overview of climate policy in Ireland and mapped the factors which have the potential to limit or drive its success. We have opened lines of enquiry in this research process which will be developed further over the course of this project in order to build a comprehensive picture of the underlying narratives which have the power to which dictate Irish people's beliefs about and attitudes towards climate change. These beliefs and the stories that inform them ultimately have the power to spell the failure or success of Ireland's environmental policies.

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